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Project Nr. 2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000086863

Erasmus+ Project

lightcode

Strengthening the Digital
Transformation of Higher Education
Through Low-Code

Work Package 5

LIGHTCODE SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

REACH Innovation

Final Version
October, 2025

Dauphine | PSL
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INTRODUCTION

The **LightCode Erasmus+ Project** addresses a pressing challenge of Higher Education, namely: how to equip students and educators across all disciplines—not just in Computer Science—with the **Digital Skills** required in an increasingly technology-driven society, not only in Europe but Worldwide. The LightCode project promotes a practical, inclusive, and accessible approach to digital transformation by introducing **Low-Code development tools** as a gateway to technical literacy, innovation, and employability.

To this end, **LightCode has produced three major outputs**, each designed for integration and reuse across diverse educational contexts.

Main Outputs of the LightCode Erasmus+ Project:

- **(A) Training Materials for Faculty Members:** A set of modular, interdisciplinary resources that help educators integrate low-code technologies into their teaching practice while promoting inclusive and gender-sensitive pedagogy.
- **(B) The LightCode Course for Students:** A structured curriculum introducing students to low-code development, digital problem-solving, and cross-sectoral collaboration, suitable for adaptation across faculties.
- **(c) The LightCode Platform:** A custom-built, web-based platform that enables students and faculty to collaboratively learn, experiment, and build low-code applications in an openly accessible environment.

To ensure impact beyond the project's life, this strategy proposes actions, identifies risks and opportunities, and outlines governance mechanisms that allow for wide adoption and ongoing use.

At the final development stage of the project, LightCode Partner [REACH Innovation](#) used its experience with *Digital Platforms and Exploitation Procedures* to produce for the LightCode project a **Sustainability Plan**, which

defines a feasible **Sustainability Strategy** in order to guarantee that the results of the project can be **maintained, reused, scaled, and embedded** in the Higher Education sector, ensuring their continued value beyond the project's lifetime and enabling long-term impact on digital education practices across Europe.

A core goal of the Sustainability Plan for Erasmus+ Projects, is to ensure that the project's positive effects continue, whether by transferring results to new contexts or sustaining them after the project funding period ends. The sustainability and monitoring strategy defined in the current "**LightCode Sustainability Plan**" will provide the project partners, and related stakeholders, with a clear pathway for sustaining and scaling up project results after the end of the project.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

This section outlines the long-term goals that drive the sustainability actions put forward for the LightCode Project. By anchoring the project outcomes in existing educational ecosystems and EU digital policies, the strategic objectives align LightCode's value proposition with institutional and policy priorities.

LightCode Main Strategic Sustainable Exploitation Goals:

- **S1:** *Integrate LightCode outcomes into higher education curricula and institutional practices across Europe, starting with the EU countries involved in the LightCode Project (the EU Partners' Countries).*
- **S2:** *Support capacity-building in digital and interdisciplinary teaching.*
- **S3:** *Maintain and update the LightCode platform in a sustainable way.*
- **S4:** *Promote open access and widespread replication across Europe and beyond.*

Notice that while S1 focuses on a short-term period of exploitation of the project results, having already partially started during the project funding period, S4 is devoted to a long-term exploitation of the project, mainly focusing on the period beyond the project lifetime (after October 2025).

SWOT ANALYSIS

This section presents a strategic assessment of each project result's potential sustainability, identifying internal strengths and weaknesses, and external opportunities and threats. In order to perform such analysis, the SWOT methodology was used [4] [5], based on the study of "Strengths", "Weaknesses", "Opportunities" and "Threats", to address the needs of potential users and final beneficiaries and the exploitation measures to be followed. The SWOT Analysis is a well-known methodology created in the 1960s by Albert Humphrey of the Stanford Research Institute, as described in [4]. It is used to identify recommendations and strategies, with a focus on leveraging strengths and opportunities (internal factors) to overcome weaknesses and threats (external factors) [5], informs mitigation and scaling strategies.

Here a template used for creating a SWOT analysis is illustrated, and the four factors involved (Strengths, Opportunities, Weaknesses, and Threats) are explained. **Strengths** are capabilities that enable the project to perform well and need to be leveraged into attributes, characteristics and factors that give competitive advantage to the business. **Weaknesses** are characteristics that prohibit the project from

performing well and need to be addressed into attributes, characteristics and factors that weaken competitiveness of the project. **Opportunities** are trends, forces, events, and ideas that the project can capitalize on, including favourable situations and factors that can strengthen or provide the project with new sources of competitive advantage. **Threats** are possible events or forces outside your control that the project needs to plan for, or decide how to mitigate, including unfavourable situations and factors that could create problems for the project, compromising its competitive advantage to a certain extent. With the SWOT Analysis, a project can evaluate its competitive position, by assessing internal and external factors, as well as current and future potential.

Within a project's perspective, the SWOT framework enables a systematic identification of the internal strengths and weaknesses that influence the project's performance, as well as external opportunities and threats that could impact its future trajectory. By understanding these factors, a more strategic approach can be adopted to leverage the project's advantages, to address its challenges, to capitalise on emerging trends, and also to mitigate potential risks. Hence, the SWOT analysis provides a solid foundation for informed decision-making and the development of a robust market strategy. As a result, potential users of the project will be involved and will receive information for the exploitation of the project results.

In the sequel of this section three brief SWOT Analyses are presented for each of LightCode's main outputs.

A. Training Materials for Faculty Members – SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
✓ Produced by LightCode Partners with high experience with Higher Education matters.	✗ Needs proactive dissemination and institutional awareness

<p>✓ Aligned with the European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu) [1]</p> <p>✓ Adaptable across disciplines of Higher Educational Curricula</p> <p>✓ Supports Gender Equality & Inclusive Pedagogy</p>	<p>✗ May face resistance from tech-averse educators</p>
<p>Opportunities</p> <p>► Can be fairly easily integrated into Higher Educational Curricula and into Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Schemes</p> <p>► Allows for Partnerships with Educational Networks (e.g., EUA*, *European University Association (https://www.eua.eu/), and ENQA**, **European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (https://www.enqa.eu/))</p>	<p>Threats</p> <p>⚠ Low institutional priority for Continuing Professional Development (CPD)</p> <p>⚠ Needs periodic updates to remain relevant (involving medium-to-high maintenance efforts)</p>

B. The LightCode Course for Students – SWOT Analysis

<p>Strengths</p> <p>✓ Supports key EU digital skills targets (https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-skills)</p>	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p>✗ Competing demands on curriculum space</p>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Produced by LightCode Partners with high experience with Higher Education Courses. ✓ Interdisciplinary by design ✓ Flexible modular design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Requires digital access and support services
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Eligible for ECTS and micro-credentialing ▶ Can be offered across Erasmus+ networks 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Rapid obsolescence due to tech evolution ⚠ Low engagement if not linked to employability outcomes

C. The LightCode Platform – SWOT Analysis

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Open-access ✓ Tailored for educational use ✓ Intuitive ✓ Encourages hands-on learning 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Requires long-term technical support ✗ May face security and hosting challenges
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Can evolve via open-source community usage 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Risk of technical debt without updates (involving medium-to-high maintenance efforts)

► To be used by Higher Education Institutions (HEI) as a capstone or innovation tool	⚠ Low adoption without structured outreach
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LIGHTCODE EXPLOITATION

Usually, exploitation in Erasmus+ projects deals with the process of ensuring that the project's results are used, benefiting the EU society. This involves developing strategies to use the results for mainstreaming: aiming to influence decision-makers to incorporate project results into policies or practices, and multiplication policy: persuading individual end-users to adopt the project's results, products or methods. An effective exploitation strategy increases the project's impact, extends its sustainability, and justifies the program's value by transforming outcomes into tangible benefits at local, national, and European levels.

EXPLOITATION PATHWAYS

This section deals with the strategy taken for exploiting the results of the LightCode Project. It is relevant noticing that the main aim of an exploitation strategy is to spread the outputs in line with the needs of the target groups and to reach the right audience in proper manner, so as to enable them to benefit from the activities and outputs of the project. In the case of the LightCode project, this section details how each core output of the project (A. The Faculty Training Materials; B. The Student Course Modules; and C. The Low-Code Platform) can be exploited sustainably by Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) and related stakeholders. It focuses on integration pathways, licensing, institutional alignment, and stakeholder engagement.

A. Potential Exploitation for the Training Material for Faculty Members

The training materials are designed to build faculty capacity in digital pedagogy, low-code education, and inclusive teaching practices. They are modular and interdisciplinary, facilitating wide application across departments and institutions.

Exploitation Actions related to LightCode Output (A):

- Integrate into faculty professional development and **Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programs**.
- Disseminate under **Creative Commons (CC-BY) licenses, maximizing impact and visibility** of project results by removing usage restrictions.
- **Align the training materials with** the European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators **DigCompEdu** [1].
- Offer **“Train-the-Trainer” pathways and guidance** to multiply institutional impact.
- **Focus on the Strengths and Opportunities of the SWOT Analysis** elaborated for the Training Material for Faculty Members, while **controlling tightly the risks posed by the identified Weaknesses and Threats**.

B. Potential Exploitation for the LightCode Course for Students

The LightCode student course equips learners with practical low-code development skills that boost employability and digital readiness. It supports inclusive access, gender balance, and can be adapted to multiple disciplines within Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs).

Exploitation Actions related to LightCode Output (B):

- **Embed into elective or core modules across HEIs disciplines** (ICT, social sciences, business, etc).

- Break into micro-learning units aligned with the **European Micro-Credential Framework** [2].
- Recognize the LightCode Course via **ECTS credits** or **digital badges in HEIs**.
- **Promote the Course** effectively through HEIs Students Unions, Career Centers, and Erasmus+ alumni networks.
- **Focus on the Strengths and Opportunities of the SWOT Analysis** elaborated for the LightCode Course for Students, while **controlling tightly the risks posed by the identified Weaknesses and Threats**.

C. Potential Exploitation for the LightCode Platform

The LightCode platform is an intuitive, web-based environment allowing students and educators to explore, build, and test low-code applications. Its accessibility and hands-on orientation make it a scalable learning tool.

Exploitation Actions related to LightCode Output (C):

- Release the **Platform under an open-source license scheme**.
- Establish a **public GitHub repository** for being used by the platform (if needed) **with clear maintenance guidelines**.
- Offer **integration capabilities** with Moodle and other LMS platforms.
- Encourage institutions (HEIs) to **host their own localized instances of the platform**.
- **Enable community contributions** and updates via open development cycles [3].
- **Focus on the Strengths and Opportunities of the SWOT Analysis** elaborated for the LightCode Platform, while **controlling tightly the risks posed by the identified Weaknesses and Threats**.

SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY GOVERNANCE & MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Effective sustainability requires clear and well-defined post-project governance. This section identifies how responsibility for maintaining and evolving the LightCode project's outcomes can be effectively distributed among the Consortium Partners and potential Partners-Institutions.

Actions	Timeline	Responsibility / Notes
A1. Form a LightCode Sustainability Council/Group	Project Month 36 (M36)	Coordinator + All Consortium Partners
A2. Publish all (non-confidential) produced content and project's results as Open Educational Resources (OERs) with CC license.	During Project Development + Project End (M36)	All Partners with the support of the Dissemination Partner <i>Public Documents (i.e.: Newsletters; Press Releases; Banners; Posters; Leaflets, etc.) have been linked in the project website and included in the LightCode Zenodo Account.</i>
A3. Identify 2–3 HEIs to host and maintain platform forks	End of project (M36) + 1 Year (Y1) post-project	Tech-oriented Partners (+ New Piloting Partners)
A4. Establish GitHub Repository for the Platform and its content	During Project Development	Technical Development Partner in the Project
A5. Apply for follow-up Projects (Erasmus+ /Digital Europe, ...) for scaling-up	Year 1–2 post-project End	Leading Consortium Partner + Interested Core Partners + New Piloting Partners

PROJECT DISSEMINATION IN SUPPORT OF EXPLOITATION

The LightCode Project follows since its beginning a comprehensive Dissemination Plan with a solid and efficient Dissemination Strategy, produced by its Dissemination Partner REACH Innovation [6]. In this plan, the defined project dissemination identified all the main target groups of stakeholders, who can profit from the developments of the LightCode project, as:

1. Students of Universities or High-Education Institutions.
2. Universities and High-Education Institutions' Professors and Faculty Members.
3. Universities and High-Education Institutions' Students' Communities.
4. Local & International Communities and Networks. Educational.
5. Local & International IT Communities and Networks.
6. Local, Regional & International Community Members (General Public).
7. 3rd Sector Organizations at Local Level and at EU & International Levels.
8. EU & Erasmus+ related Networks, Communities, and Initiatives.
9. EU & Erasmus+ related Projects & involved Partners.

Most of the target groups needed different ways to have information-contents communicated to them, via the different dissemination channels of the project. All this was catered by the adopted Dissemination Strategy. REACH has established all the social media accounts for the LightCode project, as well as the project website, within the platform-channels listed in the Table below.

Channel	Site / Account / Link
LightCode Website	LightCode Erasmus+ Project Website http://www.lightcode-project.eu/
LinkedIn	lightcode-erasmus-project https://www.linkedin.com/company/lightcode-erasmus-project/
Twitter	@lightcode_proj https://twitter.com/lightcode_proj/
Instagram	@lightcode_project https://www.instagram.com/lightcode_project/

Facebook	LightCode Erasmus+ Project https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100090357237506
Zenodo	LightCode Project Zenodo Open Science Community https://zenodo.org/communities/lightcode_erasmusplus_project
YouTube	LightCode Erasmus+ Project YouTube Channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJi9SdZ5IzSY_EYDi7LDByg
EPALE Platform	LightCode @ EPAL Platform https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/content/welcome-erasmus-project-lightcode
LightCode Platform	LightCode Erasmus+ Project Platform Access https://lightcodepedia.org/ (Status of September 2025, made available by Partner KarmicSoft during the "LightCode Academy")

Dissemination Strategy Important Factors

The Dissemination Strategy for the LightCode was based on the project's overall goals, using the Dissemination Kit already deployed in [6] to fulfil the specific dissemination aims defined within WP5. Together with the dissemination channels, some templates for the LightCode project were elaborated by REACH, and used all through the project lifetime, when producing Work Packages' Deliverables, Power Point Presentations, and periodic project Newsletters. These are available as dissemination resources via the project website (<https://www.lightcode-project.eu/dissemination-kit/>).

Dissemination Control & Monitoring

During the LightCode project lifetime, the dissemination contents have been regularly monitored using a dedicated Dissemination Calendar, and also via statistics analysis from the social media accounts; as well as qualitatively evaluated after the release of single outcomes (posts; tweets; newsletters; podcasts) with a standard regular interval. The monitoring of the work packages, of the project results and of the deliverables for their subsequent dissemination among the target groups of stakeholders was a crucial aspect of the project, playing a significant role in ensuring project success and impact. While dissemination ensured that the project's impact was maximized and knowledge has been shared, monitoring deliverables was essential for maintaining control, minimizing risks, and ensuring the project stays on course throughout its lifecycle. Together, those practices contributed to achieving the project objectives and maintaining stakeholder confidence in the project team's capabilities. The importance of both aspects related to monitoring and dissemination, relied on some key-factors:

- **Knowledge Sharing:** Dissemination allowed the sharing of project outcomes, findings, and knowledge with stakeholders, contributing to the collective understanding of the subject matter.
- **Validation and Recognition:** Sharing results provided a platform for validation by the wider community or relevant stakeholders, reinforcing the credibility of the project. Recognition of achievements enhanced the project team's reputation and fostered the attraction of potential collaborators, funders, or partners for future joint-initiatives.
- **Informed Decision-Making:** Stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public, could make more informed decisions based on the insights and outcomes generated by the project.
- **Technology Transfer:** Projects often develop new technologies, methodologies, or best practices. Dissemination facilitates the transfer of these innovations to other projects, industries, or communities.
- **Maximizing Impact:** The effective dissemination of the project increased the potential impact of the project by reaching a broader audience, thereby contributing to the project's overall success and the achievement of its objectives.

- **Public Engagement:** Dissemination engaged the public and raised awareness about the project's goals, encouraging public interest and support for the initiative.
- **Policy Influence:** Project results influenced policy decisions when shared with policymakers, helping to shape regulations, guidelines, or practices in the relevant field.
- **Feedback and Improvement:** Stakeholder feedback obtained through dissemination channels provided valuable insights for the project team.
- **Project Control:** Monitoring deliverables ensured that the project stayed on track and was kept aligned with its original objectives, timelines, and budgetary constraints.
- **Risk Management:** Regular monitoring helped identify potential risks and issues associated with deliverables early in the project lifecycle.
- **Resource Optimization:** Efficient monitoring allowed for the optimal allocation of resources, ensuring that resources were utilized effectively.
- **Stakeholder Confidence:** Consistent monitoring and timely delivery of high-quality deliverables, built stakeholder confidence in the project.
- **Adaptability to Change:** Monitoring facilitated the identification of changes in project requirements, scope, or external factors timely.
- **Quality Assurance:** Monitoring ensured that deliverables met predefined quality standards, reducing the need for extensive revisions.
- **Communication and Transparency:** Regular updates on deliverable status promoted transparency within the project team and among stakeholders.

Strategy for Long-Term Uptake

To ensure long-term uptake, the strategy includes plans for communicating project outcomes through networks, events, and open platforms.

- **Publications:** Articles in peer-reviewed journals and open educational repositories (e.g., Zenodo, OER Commons).
- **Workshops/Webinars:** Host online events to train faculty and present success cases.
- **Policy Outreach:** Present results at national and EU digital education forums.
- **Multiplier Events:** Showcase use cases and testimonials from early adopters in different countries.

In order to support the Multiplier Events to be organized by all Consortium Partners in their own EU Countries by the end of the project (and beyond), REACH Innovation has made available a special Banner (Roll-up) which can be downloaded for local printing from the project website. See Figure below.

Erasmus+ Project
lightcode
 Strengthening the Digital Transformation of Higher Education Through Low-Code
 Nr.2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-00086863

The LightCode Project fosters a more open, digital, and inclusive higher education environment, by training Faculty Members and Students in the Low-Code approach.

Project Outcomes:

- *Teachers Training Programme*
- *Students Training Course*
- *LightCode Platform*

Learn more about the LightCode Project!
www.lightcode-project.eu

Partners: Dauphine | PSL, University of Bourgogne, KarmicSoft, REACH symplexis, and Co-funded by the European Union.

See also below the 2-pages Invitation for the Austrian LightCode Multiplier Event (ME) organized by REACH Innovation, which can be used as template for all other Partners' ME's organizations.

Sustainability and Exploitation of the LightCode Project Results

To support the long-term sustainability and exploitation of the LightCode project results, the Consortium is encouraged to actively continue to use the EPAL platform (European Commission Electronic Platform for Adult Learning) beyond the project's lifetime, as well as the Zenodo.org platform, via the [LightCode Project Zenodo Open Science Community](#).

All core outputs, including the low-code learning materials, interdisciplinary teaching modules, policy recommendations, and the inclusive digital skill-building toolkit, have been uploaded to EPAL's publicly accessible resource center. Likewise, the public documents produced by the LightCode project were made available in the project Zenodo Open Science Community.

Additionally, project partners are encouraged to publish reflective blog posts and practice-oriented articles on EPAL to share insights, showcase success stories, and stimulate dialogue around inclusive digital transformation in higher education.

The continuous use of those platforms will ensure that educators, trainers, and institutions across Europe can continue to access, implement, and adapt the project's resources.

Maintaining the project's online presence will support the continued relevance of LightCode, facilitate cross-sector reuse of results, and open pathways for

future collaboration within the European adult learning and higher education communities.

FUNDING CONTINUATION OPTIONS

This section identifies concrete options for extending financial and institutional support for the LightCode ecosystem beyond Erasmus+ funding.

Recommended Pathways:

- Apply for **follow-up Erasmus+ (KA2* or KA3**)** projects focused on digital transition and teaching innovation. ([*Key Action 2: Cooperation among organisations and institutions](#); [**Key Action 3: Supporting policy development and political cooperation](#)).
- Explore opportunities under the **Digital Europe Programme (DEP)** <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme> and / or **Horizon Europe**, to improve the Platform, and in particular emphasize gender inclusion and interdisciplinary STEM skills within new proposals.
- Develop **institutional sponsorships** or **regional digital literacy programs** to cover platform hosting and technical support.

CONCLUSIONS

The LightCode project presents a timely and innovative contribution to the digital transformation of higher education in Europe. By democratizing access to low-code tools, promoting gender and disciplinary inclusiveness, and fostering both faculty and student digital capacities, it addresses critical gaps in current educational systems.

This document described the Sustainability Plan adopted for the LightCode Erasmus+ Project, using its available Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy as the core for the development of the adopted Sustainability Strategy, which envisages to grow the project's network and to gain more visibility within the main defined target groups in a sustainable way, beyond the project lifetime.

This Sustainability Strategy outlines a comprehensive roadmap to ensure that the project's key outputs: A) Training Materials, B) Students Courses, and C) The LightCode Platform, continue to deliver value long after the project ends. Through a combination of open licensing, institutional embedding, community engagement, and alignment with EU frameworks and funding mechanisms, LightCode can support building the blocks to become a lasting resource for higher education innovation.

Key to this expected success will be the commitment of project partners, the leadership of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), and the support of European networks and policymakers. With the right governance, continued dissemination, and targeted funding, LightCode has the potential not only to sustain itself, but to evolve into a model for digital and inclusive education across disciplines.

The project's main characteristics shall continue to include "accessibility, flexibility, and innovation", as important aspects, guiding all post-project actions to ensure that its benefits are widely and equitably distributed, at regional, and at European levels.

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